

FORMS OF ORGANIZING STUDENTS' ACTIVITIES AND COMPONENTS OF COURSE TRAINING

Ernazarov Alisher Ergashevich -

Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Head of the Department of Information Technologies, Ph.D

alexchigatay1213@gmail.com

g.m.soxibovna@gmail.com

Annotation:

forms of organization of learners' activities, elements of training, type of training, components of training, criteria of training and types of training are mentioned.

Keywords: educational process, lesson training, training structure , training elements, training forms, training training components, training criteria.

Introduction

Preparation for modern education is one of the main aspects of the development of students and their successful adaptation to modern society. In order to achieve optimal results and develop the potential of each student, it is important to organize student activities in various ways.

One of the forms of organization of student activities are academic clubs and scientific societies. These groups bring together students with common interests and worldviews, allowing them to explore different fields of knowledge together, conduct research and debate, and participate in conferences and symposia. Such forms of organization of student activities develop teamwork, critical thinking and self-organization skills, as well as help to expand professional growth and worldview.

In addition to academic clubs, social forms of organizing student activities are also important. Student social organizations and student councils help develop student leadership,

organize events, and protect the welfare and interests of the student body. They help to develop social responsibility, social activism and interaction with other organizations.

It is important to pay attention to the organization of students' cognitive activities:

1. Determining the provision of conditions for the camera work of thinking and thinking: planning and understanding of the objects and subjects studied by students through perception; establish the use of the form of trust and persuasion; planning conditions for students' intense attention and attentiveness; the use of different forms of work (individual discussion, conversation, tects on repetition) to actualize in the memory of the previously acquired knowledge, which is important for the acceptance of new knowledge .

2. Organization of students' thinking and understanding activities in the process of forming new knowledge and skills: determining the degree of formation of students' knowledge and skills (exact visualization, understanding, generalization, introduction of formulas); in organizing the thinking and understanding activities of learners: relying on the psychological laws of creating new patterns, imagining, and forming levels of understanding; planning forms and ends of work that ensure independent thinking and activity of learners (system of questions, creation of problematic situations, problem-heuristic levels of solving various problems, organization of research and research work in training); to lead in order to increase the level of understanding (from description, comparison and explanation to generalization, evaluation and problem solving) and the formation of reasoning and conclusion skills; use of various creative works of students (explanation of the theme and purpose of the work, conditions of its execution, selection and systematization of teaching material, processing of results, coordination of work).

Consolidation of work results: formation of skills by solving problems, training to transfer previously acquired knowledge and skills to new work conditions.

Organization of learners: their attitude to learning, their organization, the level of intellectual development, existing groups of learners according to the level of training, the condition of their hijab in determining their individual, group and frontal work together in training.

Taking into account the individual strengths of learners: planning training based on their individual strengths, conducting training based on strong and weak learners, a differentiated approach to them.

Requirements for the training technician: the training should be emotional, arouse interest in learning and educate the need for knowledge; the tempo and rhythm of the training should be optimal, the actions of the pedagogue and the learner should be completed; pedagogues and students should be tactful and optimistic in training; there should be a benevolent and active creative work environment; as much as possible, it is necessary to change the types of activities of learners, taking into account different forms and methods of teaching; it is necessary to ensure compliance with the training regime; pedagogue should ensure active learning of every learner. Forms of organization of students' activities are listed below.

Forms of organization of students' activities

<i>Specific signs of violence</i>	<i>How do we choose the form</i>	<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Disadvantages</i>
Frontal (Group)			
The teacher works with the whole group. Learning goals and tasks will be common for all. Each works according to its own principle. Some listen attentively, others are distracted. Some of them answer questions, others don't listen to questions. Some of them perform the exercises quickly and efficiently, others do not have time, and still others perform them quickly and efficiently.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - when explaining new material; - during the independent work of learners, when many make the same mistakes, the pedagogue stops the work to repeat to everyone; - at the end of the training, at the time of issuing the final results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - allows to establish a reliable relationship and communication between the pedagogue and the learner; - educates public opinion; - allows students to be taught to think; - forms interest in stable knowledge; - the pedagogue gets the opportunity to present the material to the whole group and freely influences the whole team. 	This form is intended for an average learner (learners with limited educational opportunities will not be able to do it, only strong ones will need more complex tasks.).
Individual			
The learning goal for everyone is common, but everyone is independent at an individual pace, each in his own place.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - during the independent work of learners on conducting written exercises on card-tasks, individual tasks, hiqob-graphic, control work; - while performing practical work on the same or various other tasks, but the work of each depends on the other. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enables education of students' independence, organization, diligence in achieving the goal; - makes it possible to develop important skills and competencies, cognitive activity experience; - allows students to develop a need for independent education. 	This form somewhat limits communication between students, their desire to share their knowledge with others, and their participation in collective achievements.
Couple			
The teacher organizes the work in pairs: strong-weak learners, or two learners of the same	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the couple discusses the tasks ahead while updating the basic knowledge of the upcoming practical work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - makes it possible to form cooperation skills and establish reliable relationships in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - learners are always in a state of independent review of

level of mastery.	<p>requiring serious digital understanding;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - during laboratory-practical work, it is possible to organize mutual control and mutual support; - during the release of the final results, it is possible to organize mutual evaluation. 	<p>performing common tasks;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - allows to educate mutual control and mutual support. 	<p>complex educational material.</p>
Collective			
<p>It is common for team members only. However, everyone in this brigade may have different tasks. A relationship of mutual responsibility and dependence appears in such teams. The supervision is carried out closely by the team members, but the pedagogue has the main role.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - during the formation of new tasks for the organization of game teams to discuss problems and search for solutions; - during independent work on the division of labor and the organization of permanent and temporary brigades for the execution of works requiring cooperation; - at the end of the working day, the team evaluates the level of knowledge and skills of the opponents during the organization of business games, when the final result is released. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enables education of independence and activity in learners; - enables the formation of cooperation skills with others in performing common tasks; - enables the formation of social qualities of a person. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - difficulties in filling groups and organizing work in them; - in groups, students are not always in a position to comprehensively consider complex educational material, they do not know how to choose the most logical way of learning it.

Effectiveness. Even evaluating the quality and effectiveness of a single training session is a complex task, as it is characterized by individualized new learning of the individual learner and hidden external observation. In the experience of productive teaching of the teacher, there are some painful signs of the effectiveness and high productivity of the training session .

Creating and supporting a high level of independent intellectual activity and interest in learning of learners; the size and complexity of knowledge received by students; training points of the mental movement of learners and their formation; to include personal qualities of learners that enable teaching, primarily in the formation of personal self-management mechanisms; taking into account the opportunities and abilities of learners, forming and supporting the motivation of each of them to achieve success; high positive level of mutual personal relations of the pedagogue and students.

Effectiveness of educational training is achieved by the use of various teaching instruments (methodology, technologies, methods, vocitas, tools, etc.) with proper allocation and saving of time. Personal qualities of the pedagogue, his influence and willingness to work play an important role in this.

Systematic training. One of the most urgent requirements for determining the systematicity of educational training in today's modern conditions, where the volume of scientific information is large and the teaching time is limited, is to find the optimal options for working with the educational material, to choose teaching methods, and to increase the camaraderie of using them in every step of it.

The camarali system of training is provided by the following: complex planning of teaching, training and development tasks; educational training, distinguishing the content of specific academic topics; determining the sequence of the material according to the purpose, repetition time, new learning, consolidation, homework; choosing the most suitable methods, tips and methods of teaching; implementation of the principles of differentiation and individualization in the educational process; creation of the necessary teaching-methodical conditions of teaching.

A large amount of time (20-30 minutes) should be devoted to learning new material. This material will be thoroughly mastered by students, and its future development will be ensured. The name of the first skill comes from the actualization of knowledge, basic knowledge, skills and competencies.

In the training session, the control function is not only one-to-one evaluation, but also regular feedback to the pedagogue and learner system. Then, in practical activities, knowledge is consolidated in the form of repetition and application: solving problems, doing exercises, conducting experiments. All of these together make up the optimal system for achieving the goal of combined training, which is widely used by the pedagogue.

Activation of cognitive activity of learners. Comprehensive acquisition of knowledge implies the organization of cognitive activities in which the educational material becomes the subject of practical actions and active thoughts of each learner. Curiosity plays an important role in this. The teacher's task is to create a good environment for working in a group with each learner's desire. A great help in this is to help the young student to use interactive forms and methods of interaction. In the "pedagogue-class-students" system, there is an exchange of ideas, a mutual discussion of questions, an active process of individual intellectual activity takes place. Every learner speaks, hears and listens, reads, obeys and directs.

Didactic systematization of educational material. The best way to activate the thinking of students is to organize a training session in which problem situations and ways to solve them lie in the classroom. Problem-based learning can be practiced in the ways shown in the table below.

Problem situations

Bocchich name	The essence of Bocchich	Accepting academic work To do
Understanding the problems of opening contradictions	Determining the opening of contradictions in a problem cavol.	Setting up communication breaks.
Forming ideas	Determining the direction of	Putting ideas.

	the search for immediate answers with the help of ideas.	
Test ideas	Confirm or invalidate the assumptions made in the idea.	Establishing connections with Cabal.
General summary	Filling corner content with new ones.	

A pedagogue plays an important role in creating problematic situations. Of course, its assistants: a manual, a set of exercises, didactic materials consisting of problem assignments. But the problematic situation: the special psychological state of the learner, which creates the involvement of individual-personal forces. A pedagogue who takes into account these factors and creates problematic situations in the minds of students, successfully develops their creative abilities.

Creativity and independence of students in the educational process. Increasing the role of students' independent work in the educational process involves solving three interconnected tasks: creating the necessary educational conditions for engaging in independent work with conscious interest, teaching them to use the knowledge acquired in educational and practical activities.

To successfully solve these tasks: a well-thought-out system is needed, in which the role and place of each independent work in the educational process, the use of similar methods, tools and resources, work with educational and dictionary literature, preparation of abstracts on a given topic, presentation, portfolio preparing materials, thinking of tasks for group work, performing laboratory work, developing projects, modeling educational situations should be clearly defined.

Practical orientation. Any educational activity should answer a number of questions of learners: Why? Why? On the one hand, these cavols help the pedagogue to focus on the practical orientation of the educational material, and on the other hand, they help the learners to determine its importance, understand its importance, master the concept, model, order, law, and views.

Appropriate use of educational-methodical complexes in the educational context. Modern educational training is a complex interaction of methodical materials, technical means of teaching, visual aids, educational equipment, forming a complete didactic system between the learner and the pedagogue. The best conditions for this, as a rule, are the classroom with the subject, which includes three essential components: educational equipment, methodological support, and management resources.

In the classroom, there should be educational equipment, tools, manuals, vocabulary materials that make up its internal content. In order for them to act and have an impact on the quality of the conducted training, complex systems and mechanisms are needed, from the equipped pedagogue's place to the electronic means of training students. All of these are the features of managing the educational process that a modern pedagogue must possess.

The components, criteria and symbols of modern training are presented in the appendix.

Components, criteria of modern educational training

There are the following forms of organization of the educational process: frontal, individual, group and pair. The frontal form implies the interaction of the pedagogue with the whole group: the pedagogue describes the educational material for the whole group, sets the same tasks, the learners solve one problem by mastering the educational material alone.

In group work, several groups are organized, they perform one or different tasks. The group can consist of 2-10 students, depending on the subject and the assigned tasks. Group work of learners is used for various purposes: solving problems and exercises, performing laboratory and practical work, learning new material.

The paired form of work implies interaction in the "learner-learner" system. It is consistent with the goal when one learner (powerful) fulfills the pedagogic function and teaches others (pact learners) to consolidate their knowledge.

In individual work, each learner receives tasks to complete individually. As a rule, the pedagogue takes into account their capabilities and level of preparation when determining each

assignment. This form of organization of cognitive activity implies high activity and independence of learners, classification of tasks.

It should be noted that there is no need to use each form separately in the educational process. Only their combined use will give the expected results. The joint pedagogue determines the educational tasks, subject capabilities, and the size of the material. Characteristic forms of educational process organization have their diversity: training, excursion, practicum, homework, optional training, seminar training, consultation, conference, additional training, etc.

An integral part of modern education is the components aimed at the development of the student's personality. Courses in communication skills, personal growth, and interpersonal skills help students become successful communicators who can communicate effectively with others. Also important components are teaching information skills, critical thinking and decision making. All these components of education develop in students the skills necessary to successfully adapt to the modern information society and achieve professional growth.

Thus, the forms of organization of student activities and the components of modern education and training play an important role in the development of students, allowing to open their potential, develop basic skills and abilities, and successfully adapt to modern society. These forms and components help students to become citizens, activate social activities and achieve professional success.

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